

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART III.

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Many sulphur compounds have been suggested as useful antiseptics, but few have kept their place in therapeutics, the chief exception being ichthyol. The therapeutic value of ichthyol oils has been attributed to the presence of alkylthiophens (Scheibler, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1920, 288, 84). The influence of the thiophen radicle in increasing the therapeutic activity has been demonstrated by Hartmann and Wybert (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1919, 2, 60) who have replaced the phenyl group in the cinchophen molecule by the thiophen radicle and have found that the resulting product possesses marked anti-phlogistic and analgesic properties.

In view of the above findings, it seemed of considerable interest to synthesise a compound in which the thiophen ring is fused with the quinoline residue. With this object in view, ethyl 3:4-dihydroxythiophen-2:5-dicarboxylate (Hinsberg, *Ber.*, 1910, 43, 901) has now been allowed to react with aniline at 170-75°, when the dianilide (I) is obtained. When treated with strong sulphuric acid at 100°, the compound (I) furnishes the quinoline derivative (II).

(I)

(II)

By boiling with concentrated hydrobromic acid (*cf.* Bestron and Jaegrté, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 907), the sulphonic group in compound (II) could not be eliminated, only the corresponding hydrobromide being formed by this treatment. The compound (II) is, therefore, amphoteric, as it forms

a hydrochloride or hydrobromide as well as a metallic salt. Further, it is interesting to note that the presence of a sulphonic group has been found to enhance the therapeutic activity of many organo-metallic compounds (*cf.* Solganal and Krysolgau, Freund, *Beitr. Klin. Wochenschr.*, 1928, 68, 606).

In order to form quinoline residues on both sides of the thiophen ring, action of phosphorus pentoxide on the compound (I) was tried, but without success. A similar difficulty in forming pyridine rings on both sides of a benzene nucleus has been encountered by Marckwald and Schmidt (*Annalen*, 1893, 274, 367).

In recent years, an ideal antimalarial has been sought in glyoxalino-quinolines by Narang and Ray (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 976). It has been, therefore, thought worth while to synthesise a benziminazolylquinoline derivative so that its antimalarial properties may be studied. 2-Methylbenziminazole, in which there is a reactive methyl group (Mills and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2724), has now been condensed with ethyl oxalate in presence of sodium ethoxide to yield the compound (III).

It was planned to utilise the compound (III) for the synthesis of bis-benziminazolylquinoline derivative, but the compound (III) could not be condensed with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde under many conditions tried.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2:5-Diphenylcarbamido-3:4-dihydroxythiophen (I).—A mixture of ethyl 3:4-dihydroxythiophen-2:5-dicarboxylate (10.4 g.) and aniline (7.5 g.) was heated on an oil-bath at 160° for 30 minutes and at 170-75° for 2½ hours. The dark pasty mass was triturated with alcohol and the solid was then filtered and washed several times with alcohol. It crystallised from dilute pyridine in colourless needles, m.p. 292-93° (decomp., producing an intense greenish black colouration), yield 8.5 g. It is insoluble in glacial acetic

acid and alcohol. It is soluble in cold alkali (the alkaline solution being coloured yellow) and precipitated by acids. It is unaffected by boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid. A pyridine solution of the substance gives an intense greenish black colouration with ferric chloride. [Found : N, 7.96 ; S, 8.73 ; M.W. (by titration), 350. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 7.90 ; S, 9.04 per cent. M.W., 354].

4-Hydroxythiophen-2:3(3':4')-2'-hydroxyquinoline-sulphonic Acid (II).—The above compound (I, 6 g.) was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid (30 c.c.) on an oil-bath at 100° for 3 hours. Effervescence was noticed in the reaction mixture, which was allowed to cool and poured into ice-cold water. The presence of aniline in the acid solution was confirmed by diazotisation and coupling with β -naphthol. The clear acid solution was treated with excess of sodium carbonate and filtered from slight pasty mass. The solution was next acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when a greenish white amorphous solid was obtained, which was twice crystallised from hot water (charcoal) in colourless plates, yield 1.5 g. It does not melt even at 310° and appears to be non-fusible. [Found : N (Kjeldahl), 4.72 ; S, 20.88 ; M.W. (by titration), 299. $C_{11}H_7O_5NS_2$ requires N, 4.71 ; S, 21.54 per cent. M.W., 297]. It is soluble in aqueous bicarbonate solution and precipitated by acids. It is insoluble in alcohol, acetic acid and other organic solvents. With pyridine it forms a salt, soluble in cold water. With ferric chloride, an aqueous solution of the substance gives a dark green colouration.

When the above compound is boiled for a few minutes with concentrated hydrobromic acid (d 1.38), it is converted into the corresponding hydrobromide (colourless rectangular plates, m.p. above 300°). It is insoluble in concentrated hydrobromic acid but readily soluble in cold water and on neutralisation with just the requisite quantity of sodium bicarbonate, the original acid (II) is obtained. Similarly the hydrochloride (colourless rectangular plates, m.p. above 300°) was obtained by boiling the substance with concentrated hydrochloric acid. With regard to the formation of hydrochloride, the compound (II) resembles the *cyclopentane-2'-hydroxyquinoline* derivative of Dieckmann (*Annalen*, 1901, 317, 91).

Condensation of Ethyl 1-N-phenyl-3:4-dihydroxypyrrrolidine-2:5-dicarboxylate with Anilins.—This pyrrolidine derivative, which is similar in constitution to the above thiophen derivative of Hinsberg, was prepared according to the method of Johnson and Bengis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 33, 745). Its condensation with aniline was tried according to the method followed in the preparation of (I), but no reaction was observed. The

great stability of the carboxy groups in this pyrrolidine derivative towards hydrolysing agents has been observed by Moullpied (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 435) and their inertness towards aniline may be likewise explained.

1:4-Dibenziminazolyl diacetyl (III).—Sodium (2.3 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) and to the cold solution 2-methylbenziminazole (13.2 g.) was added. To the clear thick solution, ethyl oxalate (7.3 g.) was then slowly added with stirring, when the reaction began with evolution of heat. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for one day with occasional stirring, when the whole solution solidified. The mass was then treated with large quantity of cold water and extracted with ether. The aqueous solution, on acidification with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid, yielded a precipitate which was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and water. It crystallised from hot water in beautiful colourless slender needles, m.p. above 300°, yield 3 g. (Found: N, 17.42. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2N_4$ requires N, 17.61 per cent). The same compound is obtained if 2-methyl-benziminazole (1 mol.) is allowed to react with ethyl oxalate (1 mol.). It is soluble in cold alkali and precipitated by acids.

The above compound is insoluble in most of the organic solvents except pyridine. Its condensation with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde was tried in acetic anhydride suspension in presence of fused sodium acetate, but without success. The condensation was next tried in pyridine solution in presence of a few drops of piperidine (*cf.* Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924-25, 1, 297) and although the solution was boiled under reflux for a considerably long time, the expected condensation could not be effected.

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